

LEGUME CROPS IMPROVING THE TECHNOLOGY OF VEGETABLE SALADS BY ADDING

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Currently, improving the quality of public nutrition and creating food products with high biological value is one of the priority areas of the food industry. Although salads are a widely consumed food in the human diet, the issue of increasing their protein content remains relevant. In this regard, enriching traditional vegetable products with legumes, which are rich in plant protein, is an innovative direction for improving nutrition.

Keywords: vegetable salads, legume crops, beans, protein value, lecho technology, nutritional value, preservation.

Salads are a widely consumed food in the human diet. They are prepared by mixing various vegetables, fruits, greens, grains, and legumes. The main characteristic of salads is the preservation of a large amount of natural vitamins and minerals due to the fact that the ingredients are not heat-treated. Vegetable salads, in particular, are valued as low-calorie but high-nutritional and biological value foods.

Daily consumption of salads provides the body with biologically active substances, improves digestion, and strengthens the immune system. In addition, pectin substances and dietary fiber in vegetables help

lower cholesterol levels in the body and regulate metabolism.

Traditionally, vegetables such as potatoes, carrots, cucumbers, tomatoes, cabbage, and corn are often used in salads. However, in recent years, adding legumes to salads has become widespread and an effective way to increase their protein value. This is an innovative direction for improving nutrition, which enhances the nutritional quality and biological significance of salads.

Legume crops are rich in complete proteins, carbohydrates, fats, vitamins, and minerals (Table 1).

Table 1.

Chemical composition of legume crops, g

Raw material	protein	fat	monosaccharide	starch	fiber	K	PP	Energy value, kcal
Red kidney bean	22	1,5	3,0	44,0	6,4	1350	2,0	333
White kidney bean	21	1,6	3,2	44,0	6,0	1180	2,1	333
Green peas	23	2,0	4,5	41,0	5,0	990	1,6	298

Legume crops are several times higher than beef in terms of the amount of mineral elements such as potassium, calcium, magnesium, phosphorus, and iron. In addition, legumes are a major source of

Band PP vitamins. are. Kidneybeans have a low content of fat, and the content of essential amino acids is several times higher compared to other grains and milk (Figure 1). compared to

Figure 1. Legume crops

In the course of scientific work, various legume crops were used to enrich vegetable preserves with plant protein, i.e., the assortment of vegetable salads was intended to be expanded by enriching their composition with plant protein, i.e., salads were prepared according to the following recipes:

traditional lecho made in tomato sauce in sample No. 1 – bell pepper, tomato, cucumber, carrot, vegetable oil;

lecho with added beans in tomato sauce in sample No. 2 – bell pepper, white and red kidney beans, tomato, carrot, vegetable oil.

The nutritional, energetic, and biological value of the new salad varieties obtained was determined (Table 2).

Table 2.

Of new vegetable salads samples main indicators determined in the laboratory

Product name	aProtein, %	mFat, %	κWater, %	K, mg	PP, mg	Energy value, kcal
Sample No. 1	1,18	3,24	8,77	288	0,96	65,7
Sample No. 2	2,47	2,28	10,78	330	086	70,3

Energy value usually refers to the amount of energy a person receives from a particular food. It is usually measured in kilocalories (kcal) or joules (J). When it comes to the nutritional value of food products, it usually refers to the proteins, fats, and carbohydrates contained in it, which are the main source of energy for our body. The biological value of products depends on the content of essential amino acids, vitamins, and minerals in their composition. Related literature: related.

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